

“WOMEN’S PROBLEMS IN SPORTS”A STUDY ON KOLHAPUR DISTRICT**Dr. Babaso Nivrutti Ulape**

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Introduction

Sports from time immemorial have been a unifying factor among all mankind days of ancient Greece where modern Olympics have its beginning, man began to show their excellence in sports they competed with each other and celebrated their success. Sports provide an opportunity to learn, to experience success, team work and moments of excellence. The speed of women's advancement in sports which has been started thus of course vary but it is important that it underway more or less everywhere. However many obstacles remain to be overcome,

Kolhapur is known for its passion for sports and there is healthy atmosphere for young growing children. Although the women sports scenario in Kolhapur is not very good, some Kolhapuri sports women had made notable achievements in the field includes Shailaja Salokhe Table Tennis, Tejaswini Sawant and Rahi Sarnobat in Shooting, Anuja Patil Cricket, Uma Bhosale Kabbadi, Girija Bodekar Base Ball, Reshma Mane (wrestling) There is abundant talent available in women sports in Kolhapur especially at junior level, but once they reach at certain level it disappears and it is matter of concern

Issues related to Kolhapur sportswomen

- ❖ Malnutrition & poor health
- ❖ Anemic & malnourished 88 % pregnant women (15-49 age category) are anemic according to UNDP Human development report.
- ❖ No proper diet.
- ❖ Financial status.

Lack of infrastructure facilities

- ❖ No separate arena for practice.
- ❖ Lack of changing rooms. ✓ Lack of sanitary facilities.

Lack of education/knowledge.

- Female literacy rate in India is lower than the male literacy.
- Shortage of female teachers.

- Gender bias in curriculum
- Absence of sports culture in institutions.
- Sports as co-curricular activity.

Lack of professionalism

Our sportswomen are lacking in professionalism due to the importance given to sports activities during their academic career You can't expect somebody to take sports seriously unless and until there is a support.

Media

- Women professionals and athletes continue to be underrepresented in news.
- According to the statistics hardly 10% of total news coverage is given.
- Study shows media still fail in quality and quantity of women sports.
- Women in the news are more likely to be featured in stories about accidents, natural disasters or domestic violence.
- Women athletes are also short shift in the media. Study shows that only 9% of airtime is devoted to women sports and 2% on national sports centre.
- 97% sports experts are male.
- The language used is different when they talk about female athlete's ex. fatigue, frustrated or choking etc.
- Hyper sexualized poses of women athletes are highlighted

Equity of representation

- Women have unequal status in administrative and management role.
- Underrepresented in coaching profession.
- Regarded as suitable for only certain types of roles. Ex. Compeering etc.

Security.

Feeling in secured at all levels. Ex. personal, social etc. Lack of freedom.

Male dominance

- Male dominated society.
- Access to sporting opportunities has been linked how women negotiate their lives within male dominated society.
- Many sports organizations continue to be male dominated and oriented towards men's requirements

Social perception

- Attitude of society towards sports.
- Absence of sports culture.
- Sports as past time activity.
- Sports will expose the women.
- Religious obligations.

Attitude of Government and administrators

- Poor implementation of sports policy.
- Lack of incentives.
- Lack of co-operations.
- Lack of positive attitude

Attitude of women athletes

- ❖ Poor self image.
- ❖ Lack of self confidence
- ❖ Lack of self esteem.
- ❖ Ageism

Suggestions & Recommendations:

- ✓ Job opportunities should be created for women athletes.
- ✓ Appointment of women coaches as far as possible.
- ✓ Equal representation to women's at all levels.
- ✓ Financial support from the government.
- ✓ Parent support for participation
- ✓ Proper recognition to women sports in the newspaper.
- ✓ Women sports magazine to be published every month.
- ✓ Sports academies for women should be opened.
- ✓ To encourage talented sportswomen to take-up sports as a career.
- ✓ To create job opportunities for sportswomen.
- ✓ To bring transparency and financial discipline in Sports department of Kolhapur.
- ✓ To establish external linkage for quality improvement, both within & outside the department.
- ✓ To improve the public image of Sports Department.
- ✓ To develop sports infrastructure by fixing certain minimum milestones, to be reached within a time

frame.

- ✓ To mobilize resources for giving grants to college to maintain the infrastructure created.
- ✓ Creating awareness & consciousness of physical education programme at student level.
- ✓ Integrations with education by making physical education a compulsory programme at all levels.
- ✓ Every effort should be made to ensure the basic equipment made available to sports women at every level.
- ✓ Training & development of coaches and sports administrators.
- ✓ The affiliated colleges and University P.G. departments should maintain health cards of students.
- ✓ 5% reservation to outstanding sports women for admission to professional colleges.
- ✓ Grant of special leave to sportswomen.
- ✓ Award of special sports marks on performance base. .
- ✓ Maintaining of Health Cards of sportswomen.

Conclusion

For a country whose population of women alone is more than the total population of many other many other countries, we fare pretty low where that treatment is concerned. The number of sexual abuse and domestic violence cases against women clearly throws light on the fact that women in India not enjoy even basic rights, their health, education and empowerment unfortunately take a back seat under such a scenario.